

A Brief Introduction to Citizen Science

**citizen
science lab**

Margaret Gold
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The CS Lab

CS in OS

What is CS?

Why CS?

CS in Funding

Q & A

Science for All & All for Science

citizen science lab

The Citizen Science Lab brings together scientists, policy makers, citizens, and other stakeholders in **participatory research projects** that address scientific questions and/or urgent societal issues that can only be solved by actively involving volunteers in the scientific process.

We act as a **facilitator and incubator** to co-create new citizen science projects that connect society with science. And we function as a **knowledge hub** to build a collaborative and **transdisciplinary** knowledge-sharing network for citizen science practices in Leiden and across the Netherlands.

Academia in Motion: de universiteit komt in beweging voor een betere wetenschap

Gepubliceerd op 08 november 2022

De Universiteit Leiden gaat aan de slag met Open Science en anders Erkennen & Waarderen! Dat is de hoofdboodschap van de nieuwe regiegroep Academia in Motion.

De afgelopen jaren is er geïnvesteerd in het ophalen van input en het formuleren van een heldere visie op [Open Science](#) en [Erkennen & Waarderen](#). Nu duidelijk is welke richting we als

Zie ook

18 januari 2021
Op weg naar een andere manier van erkennen en waarderen

01 juni 2022
Dialogo en experimenten moeten Erkennen & Waarderen van de hele universiteit maken

Wetenschappers

Hester Bijl
Rector magnificus

Karlijn Hermans
Coördinator Open Science

Margaret Gold
Coördinator Citizen Science

Cas Henckens
Coördinator Erkennen & Waarderen

Academia in Motion

2022 - 2027

Academia in Motion

2022 - 2027

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United Nations
Educational, Scientific and
Cultural Organization

Open Science

OPEN SCIENCE is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming:

- To make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone,
- To increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and
- To **open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication**
- To **societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.**
- It builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, **open engagement of societal actors** and **open dialogue with other knowledge Systems**

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NPOS Ambition 2030

2013 - 2021

2022 - 2030

2030

key lines of action

strategic goals

2013
Ambitie 100% Open Access

The Dutch government takes the position that publicly funded research should be freely accessible.

2018
Launch EOSC

The symbolic launch of the European Open Science Cloud, a trusted, virtual, federated environment for sharing research data.

2022
Launch NPOS 2030 Programme

The NPOS2030 Programme marks a new phase in the transition to Open Science in the Netherlands.

2017
Nationaal Plan Open Science

The presentation of the National Plan Open Science marks the launch of the NPOS.

2021
UNESCO recommendation on Open Science

UNESCO published their global Recommendation on Open Science to be adopted by the 193 Member States.

Towards societal engagement and participation

Towards inclusive and transparent scientific processes

Towards open scholarly communication

Towards FAIR and open research outputs

Citizen Science

Close collaboration between knowledge institutions, government, industry, and citizens to strengthen science and optimise the processes of creating, sharing, and communicating knowledge for the benefit of society.

Inclusive, efficient, and transparent processes of scientific (co-)creation, evaluation, quality assurance and communication

Removal of barriers to reading and reusing all scientific output, so everyone can access scientific knowledge in a sustainable way and benefit from it

Products of and for knowledge creation, like data and software, being findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), and open in as far regulations allow

Open Infrastructures

Support & Training

Community Engagement

Recognition & Rewards

Policies & Regulations

CS-NL

Citizen Science Nederland

Subscribe to the NPOS CS-NL Newsletter:

<http://eepurl.com/hOm3j5>

Join our LinkedIn Group:

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8752267/>

Follow us at

[@CitSciNL](https://twitter.com/CitSciNL)

Join us at our second CS-NL Network Day on 14 December 2023 in Utrecht

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Frits Ahlefeldt

citizen science

public engagement

European Citizen Science Association

The 10 Principles of Citizen Science

<https://osf.io/xpr2n/>

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS ACTIVELY INVOLVE CITIZENS IN SCIENTIFIC ENDEAVOUR THAT GENERATES NEW KNOWLEDGE OR UNDERSTANDING

1

Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS HAVE A GENUINE SCIENCE OUTCOME

2

For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.

BOTH THE PROFESSIONAL SCIENTISTS AND THE CITIZEN SCIENTISTS BENEFIT FROM TAKING PART

3

Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy

Cite this item

FROM THE BOOK

Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy

Susanne Hecker

Muki Haklay

Anne Bowser

Zen Makuch

Johannes Vogel

Aletta Bonn

Ten principles of citizen science

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Highlights

- The Ten Principles of Citizen Science were developed by an international community of citizen science practitioners and researchers to set out their shared view of the characteristics that underpin high-quality citizen science. They are currently available in 26 languages.
- The Ten Principles provide a framework against which to assess new and existing citizen science initiatives with the aim of fostering excellence in all aspects of citizen science.
- At a time when citizen science is rapidly expanding but not yet mainstreamed within traditional research or policy processes, the Ten Principles provide governments, decision-makers, researchers and project leaders with a common set of core principles to consider when funding, developing or assessing citizen science projects.

nature > news feature > article

 nature
International journal of science

NEWS FEATURE • 23 OCTOBER 2018

No PhDs needed: how citizen science is transforming research

Projects that recruit the public are getting more popular, but the field faces some growing pains.

UCLPRESS

Edited by Susanne Hecker, Muki Haklay, Anne Bowser, Zen Makuch, Johannes Vogel and Aletta Bonn

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Editors

The Science of Citizen Science

OPEN ACCESS

SCIENCE

ATION IN
RESEARCH

Citizen
SCIENCE

How Ordinary People are Changing the Face of Discovery

CAREN COOPER

Advisor to the Public Television Mini-Series *The Crowd & The Cloud*

The CS Lab

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All Hands on Deck!

Room for everyone's talent

towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics

> **Diversifying and vitalising career paths**

We enable more diversity in career paths and profiles for academics.

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

Our vision is that the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

The impacts of CS are very wide-ranging

The impacts of CS are very wide-ranging

Filling in gaps in the data

The smartphone screen displays four challenge cards:

- Zomerzoemers**: Vliegen en bijen. 24 users, 129k views. Image shows a grasshopper and a bee on a yellow flower.
- Meikeverchallenge**: Kevers. 137 users, 713 views. Image shows a ladybug on a purple flower.
- Digitale paddenstoelenpluk**: Paddenstoelen en schimmels. 379 users. Image shows a cluster of mushrooms.
- 273k**: Image shows a small bird.

A spider is shown to the left of the smartphone screen.

ObsIdentify daagt je uit

Kies jouw challenge. Zo maken jouw waarnemingen, samen met die van anderen, deel uit van onderzoek naar deze soorten.

A mouse is shown in the bottom right corner.

BioBlitzes » Leiden 2022 - European City of Science doel: 3000 soorten

2022 Soorten gezien **2953** Waarnemingen **35316** Waarnemers **1956** Transecten **3** Punttellingen **0**

Waarneming toevoegen

98%

In 2022 is Leiden de Europese Stad van de Wetenschap - een wetenschapsfestival van 365 dagen, boordevol kennis, kunst en kunde, voor iedereen met een nieuwsgierige geest. Het doel van Leiden2022 is om wetenschap en samenleving te verbinden - en dat doen wij ook door samen met zoveel mogelijk natuurliefhebbers, (amateur)biologen en waarnemers in Leiden en omstreken de lokale biodiversiteit in kaart te brengen. Nederland heeft nog 12% over van de oorspronkelijke biodiversiteit van zo'n 100 – 150 jaar geleden en verliest nog steeds. In 2009 was de ambitie van het Leidse stadsbestuur: Leiden moet de biodiversiteit hoofdstad van Europa worden. De stad is sindsdien flink vergroend - het ontwerp en aanleg van het zes en een halve kilometer lange Singelpark is hier een goed voorbeeld van. Om in kaart te brengen hoe het nu met 'Moeder Natuur' gesteld is in die nieuwe groenere stad, gaan we graag vanaf Moederdag 8 mei 2022 met jou op pad om dat te onderzoeken! Voor meer informatie neem contact op met info@citscilab.org

Soorten

Planten	805
Nachtvlinders en micro's	404
Vliegen en muggen	269
Paddenstoelen	264
Kevers	216

Toon alles

Waarnemingen

Planten	10.570
Vogels	9.445
Nachtvlinders en micro's	2.489
Vliegen en muggen	2.236
Bijen, wespen en mieren	2.001

Toon alles

The rise of citizen science on the GBIF network

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

'Red List Index' - indicators that capture the risk of extinction over time of birds, mammals, amphibians and corals.

Red List Index, 2019

The Red List Index (RLI) defines the conservation status of major species groups, and measures trends in the proportion of species expected to remain extant in the near future without additional conservation action. An RLI value of 1.0 equates to all species being categorised as 'Least Concern', and hence that none are expected to go extinct in the near future. A value of 0 indicates that all species have gone extinct.

Our World in Data

Source: UN Statistics Division

CC BY

Data-informed action & policy

Traditional and Non-traditional Data Sources

10 benefits of citizen science

Citizen science offers many opportunities, for researchers as well as for citizens. A top 10 list of benefits.

1. Achieving more participation in research
2. Facilitating research on a bigger scale by adding additional people
3. Tapping into new sources of information, knowledge and perspectives. *“At RIVM, we conduct research on behalf of citizens. That is why it is important to get citizens involved in research. Not least to find out what the key issues are in society.”*
Mart Stein, RIVM
4. Increasing citizen engagement in scientific research and building stronger connections between citizens and scientists. *“RIVM should embrace citizen science even more. It is the best way to be at the very heart of society.”* Liesbeth Claassen

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7. Ensuring that citizens understand scientific research even better

8. Ensuring that scientists and knowledge institutes understand current issues in society even better. *“Citizen science helps scientists become better citizens.”* Lea den Broeder, RIVM

9. Focusing research on more relevant subjects and on citizens’ priorities. *“We are entitled to clean air.”* Dieter Piëntka, citizen scientist in ‘s-Gravenpolder

10. Improving scientific literacy: citizens are increasing their own knowledge and understanding about science. *“The sensors that you see here may seem highly complex. But it is a construction that has been built up slowly over time. It has taken months.”* Teus Hagen, citizen scientist in Grubbenvorst.

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8. Ensuring that scientists and knowledge institutes understand current issues in society even better. *“Citizen science helps scientists become better citizens.” Lea den Broeder. RIVM*

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What is important to research?

nature > news feature > article

 nature
International journal of science

NEWS FEATURE • 23 OCTOBER 2018

No PhDs needed: how citizen science is transforming research

Projects that recruit the public are getting more popular, but the field faces some growing pains.

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Kloetzer et al. 2021

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News & events > News > Regieorgaan Open Science officially launched as Open Science NL

Regieorgaan Open Science officially launched as Open Science NL

23 March 2023

Representatives of fifteen knowledge institutions and the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science have signed the covenant for Open Science NL. It contains further agreements about the newly established Regieorgaan Open Science at NWO, which is called Open Science NL. The festive signing took place during a meeting at TU Delft, which was entirely dedicated to open science.

With the signing of the covenant, the newly established Open Science NL is to further accelerate the transition to o

Characteristics

Theme

[Open Science](#)

Type

[Organisation](#)

Work programme Open Science NL: think along

Open Science NL is working on a programme to accelerate the transition to open science. Do you have suggestions or ideas? Get in touch.

[→ Read more](#)

CITIZEN SCIENCE ELEVATING RESEARCH & INNOVATION THROUGH SOCIETAL ENGAGEMENT

Interaction between citizens, scientists and policy makers is essential to enrich research and innovation, and reinforce trust of society in science. I am proud of the hundreds of thousands involved citizens that already contributed to research and innovation and look forward to continue opening up research towards society and the world.

Mariya Gabriel Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth

Citizen Science in the European R&I policy

Citizen Science (CS) is a core dimension of

the **Pact for R&I in Europe** that lists **societal responsibility** as a main principle and **active citizen and societal engagement in R&I** as a priority area for joint actions

the **open science policy** of the **European Commission**, embedded in the **new European Research Area (ERA)** policy agenda to achieve greater **societal impact and increased trust in science**

the **Horizon Europe Programme**, with the aim of deepening science-society relations and maximising the benefits of their interactions by **engaging and involving all societal actors such as citizens and civil society organisations in co-designing and co-creating responsible research and innovation agendas and contents, promoting science education, making scientific knowledge publicly accessible, and facilitating participation by citizens and civil society organisations in its activities**"

Citizen Engagement in HORIZON EUROPE

Open science, which includes citizen science and citizen/societal engagement, is the *modus operandi* of the HE programme

Co-design and co-creation, and **engagement of citizens and civil society organisations**, are **mainstreamed** across the programme, notably in the **Cluster and EU R&I Missions programmes**

EU R&I Missions: Portfolio of actions intended to achieve a set of goals within a given timeframe with impact for science and technology and civil society

Citizen and societal engagement is a key part of **co-design, co-creation and co-assessment activities** in the **EU R&I missions**

A number of **participatory instruments** are foreseen by the **Mission Implementation Plan**

HE workprogramme in 5 mission areas:

Adaptation to Climate Change

Cancer

Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030

100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030

A Soil Deal for Europe

tinyurl.com/nposreport

*Kennis en krachten gebundeld –
citizen science in Nederland*

Wetenschap en samenleving in cocreatie

Eindverslag van de werkgroep Citizen Science

26 oktober 2020

NPOS (2020) Kennis en krachten gebundeld – citizen science in Nederland

<https://zenodo.org/record/5495589>

The NPOS CS WG Matrix

The NPOS CS working group transformed the ECSA principles into success factors to be taken into account when designing and assessing projects, presented in a Matrix.

The matrix indicates in which phase of the scientific process these factors can mainly play a role, and in each case, it describes several criteria that must be taken into account in each project.

Not all success factors are relevant or of equal importance for all projects, but it IS important that each of the principles is considered in order to arrive at a substantiated decision about the design and implementation of the project.

Developing Citizen Science projects

What are the principles and quality factors of Citizen Science?

What do you need to think about when you're planning a project?

During the planning phase it's important to be thinking of ALL phases

Planning phase

Start of the project

During the project

Final phase of the project

Quality & Success Factors for Citizen Science

based on the ECSA 10 Principles

		Project Phase			
	Principle	Planning Phase (Project Plan)	Start of the project (recruitment)	During the project	Final phase (dissemination)
1a	Actively involve citizen scientists	The Project Plan Includes the definition and description of the project goal, target audience, media channels, and partners	Effort is being made to be inclusive to people from many different backgrounds. There is attention to training and support.	Needs and preferences of participants with regard to their involvement in the project are actively monitored and addressed during the project.	The Communication Plan includes activities to support interaction and communication between scientists and citizen scientists.
1b	Citizen scientists and scientists (in interaction) deliver a contribution to the project	There is a clear definition about roles that are expected of citizen scientists and scientists and how citizen scientists can formulate new roles.	There is clear communication to participants during recruitment about what is being expected of them and what they can expect from scientists.	Citizen scientists actively contribute to the scientific process. They play a role as co-scientist, critical friend or other.	Citizen scientists are being involved in the dissemination of the project when possible

October 26, 2020

Other Open Access

Quality & Success Factors for Citizen Science

ID Gold

The Quality & Success Factors Matrix developed by the National Programme Open Science (NPOS) Citizen Science Working Group, as contained in the report 'Kennis and Krachten Gebundeld'.

Preview

Page: 1 of 2 Automatic Zoom+

Quality & Success Factors for Citizen Science

based on the ECSA 10 Principles

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<https://zenodo.org/record/6777539>

eu-citizen.science

Welcome to the platform for sharing citizen science projects, resources, tools, training and much more

- Projects
- Resources
- Training
- Organisations
- Platforms
- Users

★ Our Gold Star Selection

join the community
and participate

Join the community of people interested in **citizen science**, to share tools and resources, project know-how and project examples for new and experienced practitioners alike!

EU-Citizen.Science

The platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources

PROJECTS

Browse and search for **citizen science projects across Europe**, representing a wide range of fields, stages of research, and types of tasks.

Share your own citizen science projects, get in touch with other project managers, and collaborate on new initiatives.

RESOURCES

Browse and search for a wide range of **resources that are useful** in various stages of planning and running citizen science projects.

Share your own resources with the community – such as tools, guidelines, policy briefs, training resources, publications, and more.

FORUMS

Have a question?

The community discussion forums that will go live with the second release of the platform (summer of 2020) will enable the community to share citizen science tips, experiences and results with each other, answer questions, and start new collaborations.

OUR PLATFORM SEARCH ENGINE

search for citizen projects, resources, tools, training and more...

search

Search for citizen science projects **by title or keywords**, or **browse by country, activity status, or topic of research** - such as biology, education, or physics.

Search for citizen science resources by title or keyword, or browse **by language, resource type, or theme** - such as engagement, communication, or data quality.

BY THE COMMUNITY, FOR THE COMMUNITY

Our mission is to become the **central reference point for anyone setting up or running a citizen science project** - such as practitioners, researchers, educators, communities and citizens - all sharing their know-how and experience.

It doesn't matter if you have years of experience or are completely new to citizen science. Come showcase your projects, share your best

Help us **strengthen the knowledge base for citizen science** approaches across all domains of science, and further encourage the **democratization of science in Europe**.

Are you involved in a citizen science project? Join eu-citizen.science now.

Visit <http://eu-citizen.science>

MEET THE TEAM

**citizen
science lab**

Margaret Gold

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